

Theoretical and Empirical Fall Rates of XCP's and XBT's

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ABSTRACT

Recent intercomparisons of depths of expendable bathythermographs (XBT) and electromagnetic current profilers with more accurate shipboard profilers have shown that the empirical formulae currently used are in error. A theoretical model for the bulk dynamics of XBT's (T-7) and XCP's is proposed and assessed with recent intercomparisons between XCP's with accurate Conductivity-Temperature-Depth profilers (CTD's). The records for the intercomparisons were obtained in the Gulf of Mexico, where a rich temperature fine-structure provides numerous features in the profiles that quantitatively improve the XBT/CTD and XCP/CTD comparisons. The theory yields fall rate and total depth versus time predictions that agree with observations somewhat better than the manufacturer's empirical formulae. The theory also furnishes a rational basis for establishing deployment techniques and probe modifications that can improve depth accuracy and fall rate.

1. INTRODUCTION

During the past decade the production technology for expendable oceanographic profiling instruments has improved significantly, consequently, expendables are becoming increasingly important in oceanographic survey work. As the measurement consistency of these devices has improved, the users have increased their demands of quality of the data obtained by the probes. Probe fall rate and depth as a function of time have received relatively little attention in technical literature to date. The expendable probes such as XBT's (bathythermographs), XCP's (Current plus BT), XSV's (Sound speed + BT) are not currently equipped with pressure sensors; thus, the probe depth must be estimated from empirical formulas based on observed fall rates and depths as a function of time. These empirical formulas do not in general provide the best possible estimates of probe fall rate or depth. Motivated by our own needs to improve probe fall rate and depth estimates, we have undertaken development of experimental methods and theories that will help reduce fall

rate and depth errors. In this paper we present results of a simple dynamical model for streamlined bodies, such as expendable profilers, falling through water. The model is applied specifically to XCP's in this paper, but we note that it is also applicable to other types of expendables (Green, 1981). Next we describe calibration methods that reduce depth error by analytical treatments of XCP data and profiles from reference instruments, such as conductivity-temperature-pressure profilers (CTD's). We show that the dynamical model is in general an excellent predictor of probe depth as a function of time. We conclude our discussion with some recommendations that could improve XCP probe performance.

2. THE DYNAMICAL MODEL

A body falling vertically through water is subject to the bulk forces of hydrodynamic drag and buoyancy, which are in balance described by the following equation:

$$Mdv/dt = \frac{1}{2} \rho_w C_D S v^2 - g(M - M_w) \quad (2.1)$$

The bulk drag force is proportional to the square of the fall velocity (v), and the buoyancy is determined by the difference between the body mass and the mass of the water displaced. (A list of definitions of the symbols are in Appendix A.) The expendables currently in use operate over a range of Reynolds number (R) between 10^5 and 10^6 , where R is defined for a streamlined body as the product of probe length and fall speed divided by the kinematic viscosity of the water. The kinematic viscosity increases with depth in the ocean and the fall speed is relatively constant after initial transient adjustment, consequently, the R tends to decrease with increasing depth. If the probes were perfect streamlines bodies moving through quiescent sea water, then we should expect that the drag coefficient (C_D) would vary significantly with depth and alter the drag force. This tendency appears to be attenuated by probe rotation caused by the axial stabilizing fins, which disturb ("turbulize") the boundary layer flow over the probe and increase the wake turbulence. The net effect is that the flow regime around the probes is fully turbulent. The C_D of the probe is much less affected by variations in Re in fully turbulent flow (Hoerner, 1965), but we should

keep in mind that small changes in C_D over the range of the probe can make significant changes in fall rate.

The buoyancy of a probe also changes due to unspooling of the signal transmission wires. The mass of wire loss is partially replaced by water that is entrained within the probe. To a good approximation the mass loss rate is proportional to the depth. Under extreme operating conditions this simple assumption may be in error (Green, 1981).

Green (1981) found an approximate solution to (2.1) for the special case in which the initial probe speed is equal to the nominal fall rate [$v(z=0) = V_T$]. The mass slowly decreases and the drag coefficient slowly increases linearly with depth; for the model the changes are assumed to be linear:

$$M = M_0(1 + Az), \quad C_D = C_0(1 - Bz),$$

$$z < 0; \quad A, B, \ll 1$$

The approximate solution for fall rate as a function of depth is:

$$v \approx -V_T [1 + (A + B)z]^{1/2} \quad (2.2)$$

and

$$z \approx -V_T t + (A + B) V_T t^2 \quad (2.3)$$

These approximate solutions clearly show the dependence of v and z on the variable parameters. To first order in t the probe depth is determined by the nominal terminal speed [$V_T = (2M_0g'/\rho_w C_0 S)$]. The coefficient of the quadratic term is also proportional to the relative changes in drag coefficient and mass ($A + B$). The empirical equations for probe depth as a function of time are typically quadratic, so we can compare the analytical results with empirical fits of observations.

Generally the effects of initial transient adjustment of the speed on the predicted depth cannot be obtained except by numerical integration of (2.1). Results of a numerical integration of with $v(z = 0) = -15 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ are displayed in Fig. 1. The variations of A and B are less than the nominal values for an XCP (Table 4), but the shape of the curve is the same.

3. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

Present expendables, such as XBT's and XCP's, measure temperature - not depth or pressure. The probe depths can be inferred from equations giving fall time as a function of depth (pressure), but a more accurate method is based on a mapping of the temperature profile of an expendable on a temperature-pressure record obtained with a CTD in spatial and temporal proximity with the probe drop. In

XCP FALL RATE vs. DEPTH

$A = 0.000271$	$B = 2.000066$
$C_d = 0.350002$	$\text{Area} = 0.002110$
$M_0 = 0.633000$	$M_0 = 1.477000$
$V_0 = 15.000000$	$R_{\text{ho}} = 1025.0$

FIGURE 1

the experimental results presented here the CTD was lowered to 350 dbar; at this time the XCP was launched. The XCP passed the CTD before it reached 750 m depth. This method provided near-simultaneity.

The use of concurrent CTD casts, would, if required, make the profiler unsuitable for large scale rapid surveys. Thus, it is important to determine whether a suitable equation for pressure (or depth) as a function of time of drop can be obtained from a relatively small number of intercomparisons with concurrent CTD casts.

We are certainly not the first group to attempt this. Smart (private communication) has performed a similar study by comparing fall times with pressures, referencing both to specific features in the temperature profile. We have chosen to use as much of the temperature profile as possible with the object of reducing random errors.

The data set used for this study was obtained during the deployment cruise of the Acoustically Tracked Oceanographic Mooring (ATOM '79) project (Saunders, Green and Bergin, 1980). Concurrent CTD and XCP casts were made in a region of strong thermal and velocity

gradients in the central Gulf of Mexico in December, 1979. The thermal regime was characterized by a very uniform mixed layer underlain by a strong thermocline, rich in fine structure but belonging to a single water mass.

For each cast, an equation of pressure as a function of the time of drop was determined by fitting the 'observed' pressures and times to a function of the form.

$$p(t,N) = \sum_{n=0}^N Q_n t^n \quad (3.1)$$

The fit is formally obtained by fitting the 'observed' pressures $P_0(t_0)$ to $p(t_0,N)$ where t_0 is the observed time and P_0 is the observed pressure from the CTD cast. These are related by the equations:

$$P_0 = P_0[T_0(\text{CTD})]$$

$$t_0 = t_0[T_0(\text{XCP})]$$

$$T_0(\text{CTD}) = T_0(\text{XCP}) + T_0(\text{offset})$$

It is easily understood, that this procedure will work only if $T_0(\text{CTD})$ and $T_0(\text{XCP})$ are monotonic functions of P_0 and t_0 , respectively. We were fortunate that there were large sections of the temperature profiles in all the casts analyzed where this requirement was satisfied. The mixed layer provided a convenient thermostat wherein the constant offsets between the XCP's and the CTD could be determined. A typical plot of interpolated pressure versus time, with both quantities referenced to the same temperature profile is presented in Figure 2.

FIGURE 2

The results for the first order and second order fits are summarized in Tables 1 and 2 respectively. For both orders of fit, it is obvious that the initial offsets varied quite widely, while the fall rates appeared to vary in a narrow range.

This range may be associated to the 95% confidence limits computed using the Student's t-distribution with 24 degrees of freedom. These limits are denoted as $\mu_{+.05}$ and $\mu_{-.05}$ and have been computed for all the fitted coefficients. The nominal value for the linear term (using the quadratic formula), $4.544 \text{ dbar}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ is smaller than the lower confidence limit in Table 2, while the constant and quadratic terms, 3.1 dbar and $-6.75 \times 10^{-4} \text{ dbar}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$, respectively, fall within the corresponding confidence limits and may be accepted.

Some values for the quadratically fitted coefficients, together with the associated parameters from the model equations are given in Table 3. For the original model, the constant term must be rejected at the 95% level, while the linear and quadratic terms cannot be rejected. After some experimentation with the model, it was found that an initial velocity of about $15 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ produced acceptable coefficients.

It is highly unlikely that the probes ever entered the water at such high speeds, however. The probable cause for the large variation in the constant term is the method for establishing the zero time point (Sanford, private communication). This variation would, for small offsets, affect only the constant term in the pressure (depth)/time equation to a measurable degree.

When the empirical fits were made, the observed pressure was differentiated with respect to time and this derivative was plotted as a function of pressure. A typical example is shown in Figure 3. The large variation in the pressure-time derivative indicated to the possibility that the probe was precessing as it fell, causing an effectively changing drag coefficient. This was incorporated into the model as a drag coefficient, varying sinusoidally with depth. The magnitude of the variation of the drag coefficient turned out to be much too great if it were to account for the same order of the drop rate as was observed. This cursory test does not lay to rest the question of gyroscopic effects on probe dynamics, since it is conceivable that gyroscopic precession coupled with the surrounding flow could cause temperature anomalies and velocity errors. This is a subject for future work. We therefore advance the tentative hypothesis that the large apparent variations in the drop speed are artifacts of the XCP temperature trace and arise from the restricted flow past the XCP thermistor.

CP/DI VS PRESSURE

FIGURE 3

4. RECOMMENDATIONS

In view of the variations observed in the pressure time derivatives with depth and the large variation in the initial pressure offsets we make the following recommendations:

- a. a signal should be made available to inform the processor of the initial time of launch and surface impact;
- b. the thermistor should be mounted in a position (perhaps near the tail) where ventilation would be maximum. This would provide for better intercomparison with concurrent XBT or CTD drops;
- c. the initial probe mass (m_0) should be controlled during manufacture to within a 1% tolerance so that variations in fall speed due to mass variations can be reduced;
- d. gyroscopic effects on probe dynamics and measurements should be analyzed, if practicable;
- e. develop a new body shape nearer to ideal streamlined form with greater diameter to increase current sensitivity and better thermistor ventilation;
- f. a pressure signal should be multiplexed and sent up the signal wire.

5. REFERENCES

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TABLE 1. LINEAR FIT TO PRESSURE VS. TIME

XCP Cast	Q_0	Q_1	p
4	5.65	4.63	0.40
8	9.60	4.63	1.43
9	7.18	4.54	2.27
11	11.88	4.61	2.23
12	15.03	4.51	2.97
13	6.44	4.57	0.87
14	12.77	4.42	2.80
15	4.66	4.58	0.59
16	38.10	4.66	1.14
17	4.19	4.50	1.22
18	4.52	4.51	1.25
20	5.02	4.53	1.62
21	-0.60	4.85	0.76
22	8.99	4.44	1.26
23	6.73	4.55	1.00
25	10.57	4.47	2.29
26	8.04	4.53	1.30
29	3.84	4.63	0.40
31	9.79	4.55	1.71
32	-4.28	4.58	1.66
34	11.27	4.59	2.81
35	8.03	4.64	1.79
36	12.29	4.63	2.46
37	5.00	4.57	0.89
38	7.99	4.61	1.55
$\frac{H}{G}$	8.504	4.576	
$\frac{2.05 H}{M-1}$	7.464	0.0883	
$\mu_{+.05}$	3.145	0.0372	
$\mu_{+.05}$	11.649	4.613	
$\mu_{-.05}$	5.359	4.539	

TABLE 2. QUADRATIC FIT TO XCP PRESSURE VS. TIME

XCP Cast	Q ₀	Q ₁	Q ₂	σ _p
4	5.65	4.63	-0.141 x 10 ⁻⁵	0.40
8	7.29	4.71	-0.653 x 10 ⁻³	1.40
9	1.55	4.70	-0.891 x 10 ⁻³	1.93
11	11.26	4.63	-0.128 x 10 ⁻³	2.22
12	3.85	4.87	-0.235 x 10 ⁻²	2.02
13	3.93	4.65	-0.526 x 10 ⁻³	0.70
14	3.16	4.69	-0.150 x 10 ⁻²	1.79
15	2.19	4.68	-0.110 x 10 ⁻²	0.57
16	32.46	4.85	-0.124 x 10 ⁻²	0.62
17	-0.22	4.62	-0.714 x 10 ⁻³	1.24
18	-1.18	4.70	-0.134 x 10 ⁻²	1.09
20	-1.00	4.69	-0.837 x 10 ⁻³	1.20
21	-0.94	4.87	-0.228 x 10 ⁻³	0.76
22	2.85	4.60	-0.849 x 10 ⁻³	0.51
23	1.67	4.70	-0.883 x 10 ⁻³	0.63
25	6.30	4.58	-0.649 x 10 ⁻³	2.17
26	6.20	4.52	-0.313 x 10 ⁻³	1.26
29	6.38	4.68	+0.124 x 10 ⁻²	0.38
31	4.95	4.68	-0.758 x 10 ⁻³	1.36
32	-12.44	4.85	-0.194 x 10 ⁻²	1.47
34	1.21	4.96	-0.148 x 10 ⁻²	1.68
35	4.94	4.74	-0.638 x 10 ⁻³	1.71
36	3.55	4.88	-0.144 x 10 ⁻²	1.56
37	3.28	4.61	-0.399 x 10 ⁻³	0.85
38	2.03	4.79	-0.117 x 10 ⁻³	1.14
μ	3.956	4.708	-8.315 x 10 ⁻⁴	
σ	7.323	0.115	7.042 x 10 ⁻⁴	
t.05 σ/√N-1	3.085	0.0485	2.967 x 10 ⁻⁴	
μ±.05	7.041	4.76	-5.35 x 10 ⁻⁴	
μ±.05	0.871	4.66	-1.13 x 10 ⁻³	

TABLE 3

A(10 ⁻⁵)	B(10 ⁻⁵)	C _D	v(z=0)	Q ₀	Q ₁	Q ₂ (10 ⁻³)
7.06	6.00	0.35	15	3.6625	4.7007	-0.979
	10.00			3.6772	4.6994	-1.169
	20.00			3.7283	4.6943	-1.613
	30.00			3.7963	4.6877	-2.017
	6.00		0	-2.353	4.7034	-0.979
			5	0.622	4.7022	-0.979
			10	2.387	4.7014	-0.979
		0.05		4.085	12.450	-6.863
		0.10		5.249	8.797	-3.425
		0.15		4.946	7.181	-2.282
		0.20		4.554	6.218	-1.711
		0.25		4.207	5.562	-1.370
		0.30		3.912	5.077	-1.141

TABLE 4. PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF XBT (T-7) AND XCP

	XBT(T-7)	XCP
Initial Probe Mass	0.740 kg	1.480 kg
Water Displacement	0.161 kg	0.650 kg
Initial Bulk Drag Coefficient	0.125 (Hoerner, 1965: torpedo)	0.35
Relative Mass Change (m ⁻¹ x10 ⁻⁵)	14.1	7.17
Relative Change of C _D (m ⁻¹ x10 ⁻⁴)	0.6	1.13
Nominal Fall Speed (m s ⁻¹)	6.5	4.7
Probe Length	0.215 m	0.510 m
Probe Cross Section Area (m ² x10 ⁻³)	2.11	2.11

APPENDIX A

LIST OF SYMBOLS

A	(M ₀ - M)/(M ₀ 700 m), the relative change in probe mass
B	[C ₀ - C _D (700 m)]/C _D 700 m
C ₀	Initial drag coefficient of the probe after impact
C _D	The probe drag coefficient
g	Gravity acceleration 9.8 m s ⁻¹
g'	g(1 - M _w /M ₀)
H	Probe range
M	Probe mass
M ₀	Probe mass at impact
M _w	Mass of displaced water
N	Order of the least squares polynomial fit
p	Pressure
P ₀	Observed CTD pressure
S	Cross section area of probe normal to axis of figure
Q _n	n th coefficient of least squares polynomial
T	Temperature
T ₀	Observed temperature
T ₀ (CTD)	Observed CTD temperatures
T(offset)	Computed temperature offset
T ₀ (XCP)	Observed XCP temperature
t	Time
v	Vertical speed
V _T	(2M ₀ g'/ρ _w C ₀ S) ^{1/2} , the nominal fall speed
z	Depth, z 0
	Mean value
	Standard deviation